

2. Variation in virulence of the field population of *X. c. pv. oryzae*, 1980-82, expressed as variance of lesions induced on IR20, IRRI.

3. Variation in virulence of the field population of *X. c. pv. oryzae*, 1980-82, expressed as variance of lesions induced on IR1545, IRRI. One extreme value (20.76 cm²) in 1982 was not plotted.

tionally with mean lesion length induced by races 4 and 6. This may indicate the inherent variability of the BB pathogen as affected by the nature of resistance of

the variety.

The *Xa 4* gene for resistance of IR20 was overcome by the predominant pathogen race. □

Ufra incidence in summer rice in West Bengal

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Ufra disease, caused by the nematode *Ditylenchus augustus* (Butler) Filipjev, usually affects the winter rice crop. But in 1984, it was recorded in the summer crop on a Ganges River island in Hooghly, West Bengal. The crop was flooded because of a high tide for 5-6 d in mid-Mar. There was a marked increase in disease 1 wk after partial submergence, when the crop was at tillering-to-stem extension.

Symptoms were leaf yellowing, especially of young leaves; twisted bases of young leaves; distorted leaf sheaths (Fig. a); and swollen lower nodes with irregular nodal branching (Fig. b). At later growth, panicles wrinkled and emerged only partially. Sometimes they did not emerge. Spikelets were partially

Infected plant parts with ufra symptoms: a. twisted base of a younger leaf; b. swollen node with nodal branching, wrinkling, and panicle distortion; and c. sterile spikelets, West Bengal, India.

filled or sterile (Fig. c). *D. augustus* was confirmed by microscope examination.

IK36 and IET4094 had only 40% infection; IR50, IET6141, Ratna, Saket

4, China Boro, and IRRI had 80% infection. Disease intensity was 20% less when the same cultivars were partially submerged for 2-3 d.

Because flooding increased ufra incidence, an expected high tide might be used to predict an outbreak in the Gangetic estuarine area. □

Pathogenic variability in *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*

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Bacterial leaf streak (BLS), caused by *X. c.* pv. *oryzicola* (Fang et al) Dye, is an important rice disease in the tropics. Virulence of the bacterium on rice cultivars is not clearly understood. We studied the interaction between the bacterial isolates and the rice cultivars to determine virulence patterns in the Philippines.

Forty-four isolates from various sites in the Philippines were evaluated on susceptible IR50, then 32 isolates were selected and inoculated on 8 IR cultivars. In all experiments, 35-d-old seedlings were spray-inoculated. Virulence was evaluated based on percentage of affected leaf area. Differences among isolates and cultivars were significant, but interaction was not (see table).

To determine the extent of variation in virulence we computed a linear regression. The distribution of virulence of

isolates on test cultivars, based on the regression coefficient (b) and mean percentage of affected leaf area, showed three distinct virulence patterns (see figure). Virulence pattern 1 consisted of seven weakly virulent isolates. Virulence 2 had

intermediate reaction, and virulence 3 was the most virulent to the test cultivars. Isolate BLS 128, from IRRI, was the most virulent and BLS 37, from Isabela, was least virulent. IR38 was resistant to all isolates. □

Scatter diagram of the distribution of 32 *X. campestris* isolates based on regression coefficient (b) and mean percentage of leaf area infection on 8 rice cultivars.

Analysis of variance of partitioned sum of squares^a for isolate of *X. campestris* pv. *oryzicola* and isolate × cultivar effects for percentage leaf area affected, IRRI.

SV	DF	MS	F
Isolate (1) ^d	31	881.702558	2.30**
G ₁	(6)	99.488097	<1
G ₂	(16)	402.660041	1.05 ns
G ₃	(7)	97.320313	<1
G ₁ Vs. G ₂	(2)	9806.023920	25.55**
Vs. G ₃			
Error (b)	31	383.726562	
1 × V	217	121.455294	1.16 ns
G ₁ × V	(42)	40.025510	<1
G ₂ × V	(112)	103.507730	1
G ₃ × V	(49)	124.133450	1.10 ns
Error	(c)217	104.253852	

^a **significant at P = 0.01. G₁ = isolates BLS37, BLS109, BLS88, BLS17, BLS58, BLS53, and BLS45; G₂ = isolates BLS95, BLS2, BLS123, BLS103, BLS102, BLS64, BLS119, BLS130, BLS99, BLS94, BLS64, BLS101, BLS129, BLS93A, BLS66, BLS69, and BLS92; and G₃ = isolates BLS48, BLS124, BLS3, BLS127, BLS128, BLS1, and BLS96.

Efficacy of the systemic fungicide CGA49104 for controlling rice blast (BI)

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We tested the systemic fungicide seed treatments carbendazim 50 WP and CGA49104 50 WP for control of BI under hill conditions at VPKAS farms, Hawalbagh, in 1983 kharif.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. VL501, a BI-susceptible, short-duration variety, was planted in 2.25- × 1.20-m plots under rainfed conditions. Seeds were treated with dry and slurry formulations of the fungicides at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg

seed. Appearance of leaf BI, development until crop maturity, neck BI intensity, and grain yield were recorded for the different treatments: T₁ = untreated check; T₂, T₃, T₄ = dry CGA49104 at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed; T₅, T₆, T₇ = CGA49104 slurry at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed; T₈, T₉, T₁₀ = carbendazim dry at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed; and T₁₁, T₁₂, T₁₃ = carbendazim slurry at 2, 4, and 6 g ai/kg seed.

Carbendazim was not effective, but CGA49104 at 6 and 4 g ai/kg seed in either form effectively reduced BI intensity and increased yield (Fig. 1, 2). However, CGA49104 was not effective in another experiment where seedlings of Thapachini, a local BI-susceptible variety, were dipped in 125, 250, and 500 ppm concentrations each for 8, 4, and 2 h before transplanting. □